

WHY TIPPING POINTS ARE IMPORTANT WHEN MANAGING MARINE SYSTEMS?

How can this Policy Brief support you?

Practitioners are faced with managing marine ecosystems and their changes due to human activities and their resulting pressures. Those systems may have an ability to assimilate and resist change and/or a resilience to rebound from the effects of the stressors. As such, environmental managers need to know when that assimilative capacity of the system has been exceeded, i.e. the tipping point, when the system moves to an alternative state, from which returning to the original state is unlikely. Hence, environmental managers need to understand such trajectories of change and when and how such tipping points occur and their consequences.

Key Messages

An ecosystem moves to an alternative stable state when a threshold of accumulated pressure (i.e. direct impact of environmental change or human activities) is exceeded.

Good Environmental Status (GES), in implementing the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), is achieved when the system is either protected from or can withstand the pressures.

Detecting this threshold by empirical data remains a challenge as ecosystems are governed by complex interlinkages, cascading effects and feedback loops between their components and pressures.

Multiple feedback mechanisms exist that can make an ecosystem resistant or resilient to state shifts. Therefore, unlike previous practices, a broad ecological perspective is needed to capture ecosystem state shifts.

It is important to know whether inferences made from smaller scale ecosystem analyses can be implemented into wider ecosystem management.

It is further important to assess the overall ecosystem structural network to determine which ecosystem components are impacted beyond acceptable thresholds; i.e., if the ecosystem component will lose function in the network or become extinct.

Consequently, there is also the need to know which critical relationships and points (nodes) are key to maintaining GES and the structure of the network.

Similarly, safe operating spaces for ecosystems are developed using tipping point thresholds as boundaries.

These concepts question whether GES can or should be achieved in the changed system past the tipping point and/or whether this requires a revised site-specific post-tipping point reference condition.

Tipping points thus require that resistance and resilience of ecosystems to anthropogenic pressures, including climate change, require to be re-assessed using monitoring to detect a priori these changes and hence avoid reaching the tipping point or following the tipping point being reached.

Narrative of the problem, with GES4SEAS examples

Most techniques for tipping point assessment are not suitable for taking a broad ecosystem perspective as most cases do not combine intervariable non-linear relationships and high-dimensional data from multiple ecosystem variables but rather tend to focus on one subsystem of the ecosystem. Thus, the perception of state shifts may be limited by methods that are often derived on small data sets, unrepresentative of whole ecosystems, or with short time-spans. Reviewing the characteristics, advantages and limitations of current techniques has produced methods that potentially incorporate a broad ecosystem-based approach. Hence, **GES4SEAS** has created frameworks to develop techniques better suited for detecting ecosystem state shifts that incorporate intervariable interactions and high-dimensionality data, such as ecological network analyses.

This framework requires approaches to assess the structural integrity of the ecosystem network and identify which ecosystem components are moving beyond a safe operating space because of cumulative pressures. This also identifies which ecosystem components may be affected through feedback loops or cascading effects.

Achieving broader ecosystem scale assessments require more adaptive monitoring programmes. Surveillance monitoring is used to scan whole ecosystems, and more targeted investigative monitoring and assessments can then focus on ecosystem components that are identified as vulnerable to exceeding their safe operating space (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Using surveillance and targeted monitoring to develop and refine network-based early warning signals (EWS) of ecosystem tipping points by identifying ecosystem components that are vulnerable to passing the safe operating space. The network shows ecosystem components that are unaffected or vulnerable or where there are potential cascading negative effects if the vulnerable nodes exceed the safe operating space (central blue shape).

Food web stability is often overestimated because traditional assessments ignore interaction strengths and realistic extinction thresholds. Species contributing most to energy transfer play a disproportionately large role in preventing cascading extinctions and should be prioritized in conservation planning. Important metrics capturing both energy flow distribution and network structure strongly predict ecosystem robustness and food web stability. Therefore, these properties should be considered in ecosystem management recommendations.

Policy implications

(* Programmes of Measures (PoM) should be designed accordingly)

European Directives

- Marine Strategy Framework Directive*
- Natura 2000 Directives*
- Water Framework Directive*
- Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
- Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive

Other Policy / International Objectives

- Regional Seas Conventions
- Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) Management
- European Environment Agency (Marine Messages 3)

Sustainable Development Goals

The GES4SEAS tools link directly or indirectly to many of the SDG:

Beyond the State-of-the-Art

GES4SEAS has made major advancements in assessing tipping points and testing of cumulative impacts of multiple pressures across European seas. Empirical case studies showed the difficulty of detecting the precise time or level of pressure that changes the ecosystem state. Despite this, European marine ecosystem states have changed, i.e. more gradual changes have occurred which could result from the impact of pressures on different levels of ecosystem organization (e.g., species, habitats, trophic levels). These have then cascaded across spatial and temporal trophic or non-trophic interactions, creating a more gradual impact across the ecosystem. Secondly, even if tipping points were identified, they tended to be species, habitat or trophic level specific, and their effect on the overall ecosystem functioning and other processes remains mostly undetermined.

The novel **GES4SEAS** tipping point assessment determines when the structural network of an ecosystem is likely to shift and which key ecosystem components are vulnerable or essential to maintaining the structure of the ecosystem. A healthy ecosystem can be characterised by ecosystem components (nodes) within the ecosystem network that evolve within a safe operating space, the assimilative capacity (Figure 2). When one or more nodes move beyond this, the ecosystem degrades until it completely shifts and creates a new stable network. This may have fewer ecosystem components or multiple subnetworks functioning separately.

Figure 2: Comparison of ecosystem safe operating space based on socioeconomic-derived pressures (yellow multidimensional space) and ecosystem structural network response to pressure thresholds (blue multidimensional space). The former is shaped by thresholds of activity intensities in the ecosystem, and the latter is shaped by the threshold of different combinations of pressures that can lead to ecosystem components (blue nodes) undergoing non-linear responses. In the upper green box, activities are within safe operating space and the pressures affecting the ecosystem network do not push any ecosystem component (blue nodes) beyond the pressure thresholds. In the lower red box, activities are beyond the acceptable limits, and the ecosystem network is disrupted with some nodes having passed beyond the pressure threshold (red nodes) while other nodes are at the limit and can tip over (yellow nodes). Here the ecosystem network shows that the regulating feedback loops of the ecosystem may have been disrupted severely as many nodes and interaction edges are beyond the safe operating space.

The tipping point assessment influences GES determination, the trajectories of ecosystem change due to cumulative effects and the influence of PoM in implementing the MSFD to create effective management actions that improve the status of our seas. This requires understanding how ecosystem status and functioning are changing and how tipping points at certain levels of ecosystem organization cascade through ecosystems.

The MSFD also currently uses indicators to determine how these populations, communities, habitats or pressures are changing on a spatiotemporal basis. This is critical for understanding shifting trends related to biodiversity shifts and environmental status. However, two important gaps in the monitoring system remain: (1) monitoring for early warning signals of ecosystem tipping points; (2) a lack of ecosystem-wide early warning signals (e.g., broader ecosystem functioning network indicators and indicators of changes in feedback loops across different ecosystem components).

Reviewing the characteristics, advantages and limitations of the current techniques has identified high-dimensionality methods such as ecological networks to provide the potential to incorporate a broad ecosystem-based approach. GES4SEAS therefore developed techniques better suited for detecting ecosystem state shifts that incorporate intervariable interactions and high-dimensionality data through safe operating space.

Key Facts

There have been few previous tipping point assessments which examine broad ecosystem-wide interactions to determine ecosystem state.

Similarly, few previous methods encapsulated a high-dimensionality assessment of tipping points.

Understanding the assimilative capacity and developing a safe operating space for ecosystems enable more effective management.

It is important to assess the overall ecosystem structural network to determine which ecosystem components are impacted beyond acceptable thresholds.

Positive tipping points can be used to increase the potential recovery of damaged ecosystems.

Authors:

Hemraj, A.D., Elliott, M., Borja, A., Cartensen, J.
doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19189962

References from GES4SEAS

Access the references and resources in this [repository](#).

For additional resources from the GES4SEAS project, visit the webpages: <https://www.ges4seas.eu> and <https://www.ges4seas.eu/toolbox/>

For more information about these and other GES4SEAS publications, scan the QR code

